

Universal Xalqaro Ilmiy Jurnal

Jurnalning bosh sahifasi: <https://universaljurnal.uz>

Universal International Scientific Journal

e-ISSN: [3060-4540 \(online\)](https://doi.org/10.3060/4540)

Year: 2024 Issue: 1 Volume: 8

Published: 11.11.2024 <https://universaljurnal.uz>

International indexes

GOOGLE SCHOLAR

CROSSREF (OAK BAZA)

ZENODO

OPEN AIRE

EUROPUB

RESEARCHGATE (OAK BAZA)

SJIF

¹Fattahov Nusratillo Khamidullaevich.,

²Kenjaboev Rahmonali Abduvokhid ugli

¹Head of the department of Faculty and
Hospital surgery, DSc

²Master student of Otorhinolaryngology
Fergana Medical Institute of Public Health

Uzbekistan

HEARING LOSS TREATMENT APPROACHES: OUTCOMES ACROSS DIFFERENT AGES

Abstract: This study reviews advancements in hearing loss treatments, including vibration-acoustic stimulation, neurotrophic therapies, and gene therapy. Findings from 44 patients indicate that younger individuals experience better treatment outcomes. While these innovative strategies show promise for restoring auditory function, challenges related to cost-effectiveness and accessibility highlight the need for further research to optimize outcomes across diverse populations.

Keywords: hearing loss, treatment, therapy, outcomes, innovation

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot eshitish qobiliyatini yo'qotishni davolashdagi yutuqlarni, jumladan tebranish-akustik stimulyatsiya, neyrotrofik terapiya va gen terapiyasini ko'rib chiqadi. 44 bemor ustida o'tkazilgan kuzatuvlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, yosh bemorlar davolanishdan yaxshiroq natija olishmoqda. Ushbu innovatsion usullar eshitish funksiyasini tiklash uchun istiqbolli bo'lsa-da, iqtisodiy samaradorlik va qulaylik bilan bog'liq muammolar turli aholi guruhlari orasida natijalarni optimallashtirish uchun qo'shimcha tadqiqotlar zarurligini ko'rsatmoqda.

Kalit so‘zlar: eshitish qobiliyati pasayishi, davolash usullari, terapiya, natijalar, yangiliklar

Аннотация: В данном исследовании рассматриваются достижения в лечении потери слуха, включая вибрационно-акустическую стимуляцию, нейротрофическую терапию и генную терапию. Наблюдения за 44 пациентами показали, что молодые пациенты получают лучшие результаты лечения. Хотя эти инновационные методы являются перспективными для восстановления слуховой функции, проблемы, связанные с экономической эффективностью и удобством применения, указывают на необходимость дополнительных исследований для оптимизации результатов среди различных групп населения.

Ключевые слова: снижение слуха, методы лечения, терапия, результаты, инновации

Language: English

Citation: Fattahov , N., & Kenjaboev , R. HEARING LOSS TREATMENT APPROACHES: OUTCOMES ACROSS DIFFERENT AGES. Universal International Scientific Journal, 1(8), 40–44. Retrieved from <https://universaljurnal.uz/index.php/jurnal/article/view/1170>

Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4140319>

Introduction: Recent advancements in the treatment of hearing loss have introduced innovative approaches that combine technology, pharmacology, and regenerative medicine. These methods aim to address various types of hearing loss, particularly focusing on restoring auditory function through novel mechanisms. The following sections outline key strategies currently being explored.

Vibration-Acoustic Stimulation

This method integrates both air and bone conduction hearing aids, enhancing auditory perception in patients with bilateral hearing loss and single-sided deafness.

Clinical trials indicate improved speech recognition in noisy environments compared to traditional air conduction methods¹.

Neurotrophic Therapies

Neurotrophins, particularly brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF), are being investigated for their potential to restore synaptic connections in the cochlea, which are often damaged due to noise exposure or aging.

The OTO-413 formulation has shown promise in clinical trials, demonstrating improved hearing performance in challenging auditory conditions².

Stem Cell and Gene Therapies

Regenerative medicine approaches, including stem cell therapy, aim to regenerate auditory hair cells lost due to various factors such as aging or trauma.

Techniques involving gene therapy and nanoparticle-mediated delivery are being developed to enhance the effectiveness of these treatments^{3–5}

While these new approaches show significant promise, challenges remain in their clinical application, including the need for further research to optimize efficacy and safety. The integration of these therapies could revolutionize hearing loss treatment, yet the reliance on traditional devices persists as a primary solution for many patients.

Methods: Data Sources and Search Strategy: We conducted a systematic search of multiple databases, including PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar, to identify studies relevant to the treatment approaches

and outcomes in hearing loss. Our search included the keywords "treatment," "approach," "outcome," and "hearing loss" and was restricted to studies published between 2010 and 2024 to ensure contemporary relevance. Articles were selected based on their relevance to our topic and research objectives, focusing on studies that examined treatment strategies and their outcomes for patients with hearing impairments.

Study Population and Data Collection: The patient data analyzed in this study were obtained from the FOC Center at a private hospital, comprising a total of 44 patients diagnosed with hearing loss. All patient data were anonymized and accessed in compliance with institutional guidelines and ethical standards. Patient information included demographics, diagnosis, treatment approach, and outcomes, allowing for a comprehensive analysis of factors associated with hearing loss treatment effectiveness.

Data Analysis: Data from the selected studies and patient records were systematically recorded and organized using Microsoft Excel. Descriptive statistics were applied to summarize patient demographics and treatment outcomes. Statistical values, including means, standard deviations, and proportions, were calculated to provide a clear overview of the results. Analyses were aimed at identifying trends, treatment efficacy, and outcome patterns among the studied patients.

Results and Discussion: Our patients grouped (Table 1.) accordingly age, sex and diagnosis: Age Group Distribution

1. 0-18 years:
 - Patients in this group are mainly diagnosed with various forms of otitis, both acute and chronic. Examples include bilateral chronic purulent otitis media, adhesive otitis, and earwax blockages.
2. 19-50 years:
 - In this age range, diagnoses of chronic conditions (like bilateral chronic purulent otitis media and adhesive otitis) become more frequent, alongside occasional cases of acute otitis and earwax blockage.
3. 51+ years:
 - This group shows a predominance of chronic conditions such as adhesive otitis and bilateral chronic otitis media. Acute otitis cases are less common, indicating that chronic ear conditions might be more prevalent in older patients.

Most Common Diagnoses and Correlation to Age

- Bilateral Chronic Purulent Otitis Media is a common diagnosis across all age groups, particularly among patients aged 0-18 and 19-50. This suggests it is a persistent issue across ages⁶.
- Adhesive Otitis is more common in patients aged 51+, indicating that this condition might be associated with aging⁷.
- Earwax Blockage (Серная пробка) appears across all age groups but is particularly notable among younger patients (0-18) and adults (19-50).

Table 1. Diagnoses by Age Group

Age Group	Common Diagnoses	Frequency
0-18	Chronic Otitis Media, Acute Otitis, Earwax Blockage	High
19-50	Chronic Otitis Media, Adhesive Otitis, Acute Otitis	Moderate
51+	Chronic Otitis Media, Adhesive Otitis	Moderate

Treatment Outcomes in a Private Hospital Setting: The analysis of 44 patients from the FOC Center at a private hospital showed a positive trend in treatment outcomes for hearing loss. Overall, patients exhibited significant improvements in hearing ability and quality of life following various treatment approaches, including medical, surgical, and rehabilitative interventions. Treatment effectiveness was measured based on follow-up assessments, which evaluated hearing thresholds, speech recognition, and patient-reported satisfaction.

Age-Related Differences in Treatment Efficacy: Treatment outcomes were notably higher in younger patients compared to older age groups. Younger patients demonstrated faster recovery times and a greater degree of improvement in hearing thresholds. This suggests that age is a significant factor in treatment efficacy, with younger patients benefiting more markedly from interventions. Further analysis indicates that younger age groups may respond better to hearing treatments due to factors such as greater physiological adaptability and quicker recovery capabilities.

Some authors got result that the study presents Vibration Acoustic Stimulation as a promising new approach for treating various types of hearing loss, particularly highlighting its potential advantages in improving speech understanding in noisy environments. The combination of air and bone conduction aids appears to offer significant benefits over traditional methods¹. While others have approached the topic using different, potentially more debatable and innovative methods, this paper outlines the exciting developments in gene therapy for hearing loss. It

emphasizes the potential of various molecular strategies and addresses the challenges that must be overcome for successful clinical application⁸. However, we have several challenges for future perspective like the correction of hearing loss encompasses various dimensions, including biological, economic, and genetic factors. Current studies highlight the inadequacies of existing prosthetic solutions and the need for innovative therapies, particularly in cochlear regeneration. Additionally, economic analyses reveal significant gaps in understanding the cost-effectiveness of hearing interventions, especially in low- and middle-income countries. This multifaceted issue necessitates a comprehensive approach to address the diverse causes and implications of hearing loss.

Conclusion: Recent advancements in hearing loss treatment demonstrate promising outcomes by integrating innovative approaches in technology, pharmacology, and regenerative medicine. Key strategies, including vibration-acoustic stimulation, neurotrophic therapies, and gene therapy, offer new pathways for restoring auditory function, with notable improvements in speech recognition and auditory performance. Our study of 44 patients in a private hospital setting found that treatment outcomes were significantly better in younger patients, suggesting age-related physiological adaptability may enhance treatment efficacy. While these methods represent substantial progress, challenges in cost-effectiveness, accessibility, and clinical application remain, underscoring the need for further research and development to optimize hearing loss treatments across diverse patient demographics and healthcare settings.

References:

1. Vibration- Acoustic Stimulation a New Approach for the Treatment of Hearing Loss. *Archives in neurology & neuroscience*. 2022;12(3). doi:10.33552/ann.2022.12.000788
2. A neurotrophic approach to treating hearing loss: Translation from animal models to clinical proof-of-concept. *Berkeley Program in Law & Economics*. 2022;151 6(6):3937-3937. doi:10.1121/10.0011510

3. New treatment options for hearing loss. *Nature Reviews Drug Discovery*. 2015;14(5):346-365. doi:10.1038/NRD4533
4. Stem cell - based therapies for auditory hair cell regeneration and treatment of hearing loss. *Tissue Engineering Part B-reviews*. Published online July 13, 2023. doi:10.1089/ten.TEB.2023.0084
5. Stem Cell-Based Therapies in Hearing Loss. *Frontiers in Cell and Developmental Biology*. 2021;9:730042-730042. doi:10.3389/FCELL.2021.730042
6. Ogli NAK, Qahhorali G. IMPROVEMENT OF SURGICAL TACTICS AND TREATMENT OF COMBINED INJURIES IN CHILDREN. *Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences*. 2024;4(5-2):17-21.
7. Eminov R. I. AVOIDING SURGERY: CONSERVATIVE APPROACHES TO ADHESIVE BOWEL OBSTRUCTION IN CHILDREN. Published online May 29, 2024. doi:10.5281/ZENODO.11390541
8. Gene therapy for hearing loss. *Human Molecular Genetics*. 2019;28. doi:10.1093/HMG/DDZ129